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Special Algebraic Structures

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SPECIAL ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURES

Abstract.

New notions are introduced in algebra in order to better study the congruences in number theory. For example, the <special semigroups> make an important such contribution.

Introduction.

By <proper subset> of a set A we consider a set P included in A, and different from A, different from the empty set, and from the unit element in A - if any.

We rank the algebraic structures using an order relationship: we say that the algebraic structures $S1 \ll S2$ if:

- both are defined on the same set;
- all $S1$ laws are also $S2$ laws;
- all axioms of an $S1$ law are accomplished by the corresponding $S2$ law;
- $S2$ laws accomplish strictly more axioms than $S1$ laws, or $S2$ has more laws than $S1$.

For example: semigroup \ll monoid \ll group \ll ring \ll field, or semigroup \ll commutative semigroup, ring \ll unitary ring, etc.

We define a GENERAL SPECIAL STRUCTURE to be a structure SM on a set A, different from a structure SN , such that a proper subset of A is an SN structure, where $SM \ll SN$.

1) The SPECIAL SEMIGROUP is defined to be a semigroup A, different from a group, such that a proper subset of A is a group (with respect to the same induced operation).

For example, if we consider the commutative multiplicative group $SG = \{18^2, 18^3, 18^4, 18^5\} \pmod{60}$ we get the table:

x	24 12 36 48
24	36 48 24 12
12	48 24 12 36
36	24 12 36 48
48	12 36 48 24

Unitary element is 36.

Using the algorithm [Smarandache 1972] we get that 18^2 is congruent to $18^2 \pmod{60}$.

Now we consider the commutative multiplicative semigroup $SS = \{18^1, 18^2, 18^3, 18^4, 18^5\} \pmod{60}$ and we get the table:

x	18	24 12 36 48
18	24	12 36 48 24
24	12	36 48 24 12
12	36	48 24 12 36
36	48	24 12 36 48
48	24	12 36 48 24

Because SS contains a proper subset SG , which is a group, then SS is a Special Semigroup. This is generated by the element 18. The powers of 18 form a cyclic sequence: 18, 24, 12, 36, 48, 24, 12, 36, 48, ...

Similarly are defined:

2) The SPECIAL MONOID is defined to be a monoid A , different from a group, such that a proper subset of A is a group (with respect with the same induced operation).

3) The SPECIAL RING is defined to be a ring A , different from a field, such that a proper subset of A is a field (with respect with the same induced operations).

We consider the commutative additive group $M = \{0, 18^2, 18^3, 18^4, 18^5\} \pmod{60}$ [using the module 60 residuals of the previous powers of 18], $M = \{0, 12, 24, 36, 48\}$, unitary additive unit is 0.

$(M, +, x)$ is a field.

While $(SR, +, x) = \{0, 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54\} \pmod{60}$ is a ring whose proper subset $\{0, 12, 24, 36, 48\} \pmod{60}$ is a field.

Therefore $(SR, +, x) \pmod{60}$ is a Special Ring.

This feels very nice.

4) The SPECIAL SUBRING is defined to be a Special Ring B which is a proper subset of a Special Ring A (with respect to the same induced

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operations).

5) The SPECIAL IDEAL is defined to be an ideal A , different from a field, such that a proper subset of A is a field (with respect to the same induced operations).

6) The SPECIAL LATTICE is defined to be a lattice A , different from a ^{Boolean algebra}, such that a proper subset of A is a ^(with Boolean algebra) (with respect to the same induced operations).

7) The SPECIAL FIELD is defined to be a field $(A, +, \cdot)$, different from a K -algebra, such that a proper subset of A is a K -algebra (with respect to the same induced operations, and an external operation).

8) The SPECIAL R-MODULE is defined to be an R-MODULE $(A, +, \cdot)$, different from an S -algebra, such that a proper subset of A is an S -algebra (with respect to the same induced operations, and another " x " operation internal on A), where R is a commutative unitary ring and S is its proper subset field.

9) The SPECIAL K -VECTORIAL SPACE is defined to be a K -vectorial space $(A, +, \cdot)$, different from a K -algebra, such that a proper subset of A is a K -algebra (with respect to the same induced operations, and another " x " internal operation on A), where K is a commutative field.

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References:

[1] Smarandache, Florentin, "A generalization of Euler's Totient Function", manuscript, 1972 .

In this mean time the following papers, inspired by this subject/paper, have been published or presented to international conferences;

[2] Castillo, J., "The Smarandache Semigroup", <International Conference on Combinatorial Methods in Mathematics>, II Meeting of the project 'Algebra, Geometria e Combinatoria', Faculdade de Ciencias da Universidade do Porto, Portugal, 9-11 July 1998.

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[3] Padilla, Raul, "Smarandache Algebraic Structures", <Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences>, Delhi, India, Vol. 17E, No. 1, 119-121, 1998.

[4] Padilla, Raul, "Smarandache Algebraic Structures", <Smarandache Notions Journal>, USA, Vol. 9, No. 1-2, 36-38, Summer 1998; <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/-smarandache/alg-s-tx.txt>; Presented to the <International Conference On Semigroups>, Universidade do Minho, Braga, Portugal, 18-23 June, 1999.